

from: maider.azanza@ehu.eus

to: ...

Subject: Study on the onboarding process (ONEKIN group - UPV/EHU)

How is it going? We are from the group ONEKIN at the Faculty of Computer Science, and we were with you a few months ago, in May. Time goes by worryingly fast.

We were talking about your experiences in incorporating new software developers in your work teams. After that interview along this time we have been analyzing the interviews collected, extracting the most significant quotes, coding them, etc. etc. etc. It is a labor with which we continue, as far as we can balance it with our academic work, and as you notice, we are going slowly.

As a first result of this study we have prepared a report, compiling the barriers you have told us that you have observed in these onboarding processes, and the strategies you have been applying. We send you the report, as promised and as a gesture of our gratitude for your collaboration.

As mentioned above, we continue with our study and try to focus on the variability aspect of the systems developed. We have found that in interviews in general we do not emphasize this aspect enough, and that is why we have prepared 5 questions, which we would be grateful if you could answer them.

We understand that it is not the best time of year, but we are really interested in your opinion and it would be helpful in understanding your context and moving forward in our work. For this reason, we do not ask you to make an appointment for an interview, it would be enough for us if you could answer us when you could, either in writing, or recorded on audio if it is more convenient and faster for you (we would then be in charge to do the transcription).

We have to plan and set a deadline, we have thought about December 23rd, to receive your contributions. We know that those are bad days, with significant workloads and then maybe some days off, and we would not like it to be forgotten, that's why the deadline is so narrow. But we understand that you have other priorities, and we would be just as grateful if you told us "for the 23rd NO, but for January 11, 12, ... Yes". We would like to gather everyone's opinion, but we do not intend to be so insistent, and if by December 23 we do not receive an answer, in either direction, we will understand that you are not interested and we will not send you a new reminder.

We look forward to hearing from you. Thank you very much in advance.

Best regards,

Maidier, Raul, Arantza